

TextBlob: A Promising Tool for Sentiment Analysis

Delna Anna Joy

Department of Computer Applications
Amal Jyothi College Of Engineering
Kanjirappally, Kerala
delnaannajoy2023a@mca.ajce.in

Sruthimol Kurian

Department Of Computer Applications
Amal Jyothi College of Engineering
Kanjirappally, Kerala
sruthimolkurian@amaljyothi.com

Abstract— As our world becomes more digitally connected, e-commerce and online shopping become more popular among consumers. As a result of the proliferation of customer interest in checking specific product reviews before buying products, sentiment analysis has grown in popularity. Sentiment analysis is an essential task in natural language processing that involves the identification of subjective opinions, emotions, and attitudes expressed in text data. In this research paper, we explore the effectiveness of TextBlob for sentiment analysis and look how it became a promising tool for sentiment analysis

Keywords— *E-commerce, Reviews, Sentiment Analysis, Natural Language Processing, Naïve Bayes Algorithm, TextBlob.*

I. INTRODUCTION

In the modern world, more and more people use the internet and shop online. Each of the sites for online shopping provides the option of leaving feedback on the product. The information gathered from feedback is valuable for both customers and businesses as it provides insights into customer preferences and helps them understand their own performance in the market. So that the customer reviews should be analysed properly to get insight from it, this process is called as sentiment analysis. Here, the TextBlob tool is used for making analysis which is a pre-trained sentiment analysis model. TextBlob uses a machine learning algorithm called the Naive Bayes algorithm which is a popular machine learning algorithm that is widely used for text classification tasks, including sentiment analysis. It is based on Bayes' theorem and assumes independence between the features (words) in a text, which makes it computationally efficient and well-suited for processing large volumes of text data. Its effectiveness in sentiment analysis and it is often used as a benchmark model for evaluating the performance of more complex machine learning algorithms.

II. RELATED WORKS

Sentiment analysis and opinion mining have been active areas of research, with numerous approaches and techniques employed for data pre-processing and feature extraction to improve the accuracy of the results. This technology has found widespread application in analyzing product reviews for business insights, and it is also valuable for consumers engaged in online shopping to make informed purchasing decisions.

Antony et. al.[1] this study shows a customer feedback review on a product utilizing opinion mining, text mining, and sentiments, which have been affected by changing their opinion on a specific product. This delivers you with a sentimental analysis of numerous smartphone opinions separating them into Positive Negative and Neutral Behavior

Sanjay Dey et al. [2] compared naive bayes with SVM classifier for Amazon product reviews giving good accuracy

Lin et al. [3] this paper is based on some features, a number of comparative tests using classification algorithms, feature representations, and review length have been conducted. We performed a statistical analysis after crawling an enormous amount of real data and discovered that mobile application reviews share the following four traits: Power-law distribution, short average length, a wide range of lengths and a substantial polarity difference.

Anant et al.[4] this paper has covered many standardization techniques for NLP, including their significance and implementation in Python using the NLTK package. A comparison of Logistic Regression and Naive Bayes models is also discussed and implemented. Resulting in the Logistic Regression being more accurate than Naive Bayes.

Kushal et al.[5] this study is a fresh method for a dynamic feature-based summary of consumer reviews that are relevant to the product's field. Results show that the suggested approaches accomplish their tasks very effectively and efficiently. The relevant passages relating to each feature-opinions combination are extracted from the reviews and placed in the corresponding feature-based cluster to construct feature-based precise reviews.

Shubhangi et al.[6] this paper covers the study of accuracy that each machine learning algorithm has in case of sentiment analysis. And says Naïve Bayes Algorithm has one most accuracy.

III. NAÏVE BAYES ALGORITHM

Naïve Bayes is a supervised learning algorithm which is developed in the Bayes theorem and its is used for classification task. NB is a generative classifier, based on the given input it will classify each to the pre-defined classes. I used NB because it is the simplest algorithms and

can be trained on small dataset so computation is fast. Bayes theorem is used for decision making and future predictions. Bayes theorem is defines as:

IV. METHODOLOGY

With the growing popularity of e-commerce websites, the importance of analyzing customer reviews and ratings has become increasingly significant for businesses to enhance their profitability. To this end, data analysts play a crucial role in analyzing large volumes of customer feedback, providing valuable insights, suggestions, and ideas for attracting and retaining customers, and facilitating business growth.

This analysis carries mainly six stages:

A. Data Collection

In this first stage, the data that is entered by the user as feedback, which is the review data are collected from the database for further procedures that are to be done.

B. Data Pre-processing

The outcome of sentiment analysis is determined by the many pre-processing procedures used.

Here,, Text is cleaned and preprocessed using Text Blob to eliminate noise, stop words, punctuation, and other extraneous information.

C. Feature Extraction:

After the pre-processing of data the relevant features, such as words or n-grams, are extracted from the text and thereby create a feature set.

D. Sentiment Analysis:

The preprocessed and feature-extracted data is used to train a Naive Bayes classifier. This involves calculating the probability of each feature and classify in to the positive, negative or neutral classes.

E. Evaluation:

The performance of the classifier is evaluated using metrics such as accuracy, precision, recall, and F1 score.

Finding the accuracy, we should know some of the general terms that are:

TP (True Positive): it gives the accurately classified input data.

FP (False Positive): it gives accurately miscategorized input data.

FN (False Negative): gives number of wrong data classified as correct.

TN (True Negative): gives accurate data classified as incorrect.

(A). **Precision:** Precision in binary classification is defined as the proportion of true positives (TP) to the total number of predicted positive occurrences (TP + FP).

(B). **Recall:** true positive rate, measures proportion of actual positive cases (TP) accurately detected by the model out of all positive instances.

(TP + false negatives (FN))

(C). **F1 score:** It balanced both precision and recall, and It is determined as the weighted harmonic mean of precision and recall, where the weight is equal to $2 * (\text{precision} * \text{recall}) / (\text{precision} + \text{recall})$. (D).

Accuracy: Accuracy is a commonly used metric for assessing a classification model's performance, and it indicates the proportion of correct predictions out of the total number of predictions.

Finally, the aspect score is calculated. This is done by using the polarity_scores, a module within the TextBlob package of the Text Blob tool.

V. USING SENTIMENT ANALYSIS

We were able to detect the overall sentiment of each product review and create an average polarity score for each product using sentiment analysis. By averaging the polarity scores of all reviews, we were able to assign a rating to each product that reflected the overall sentiment of its reviews. This enabled us to recommend to users the top five products with the highest ratings.

Our sentiment analysis approach provided a quick and efficient way to evaluate the sentiment of a large number of product reviews, and allowed us to provide users with a valuable recommendation based on the collective sentiment of other users. This technique could be applied in a variety of settings where sentiment analysis is useful, such as e-commerce websites or social media platforms, to help users make informed decisions based on the sentiment of others.

VI. FIGURES AND TABLES

```
from textblob import TextBlob
```

Import the package that are necessary.

Taking reviews (data) from database and using TextBlob find the sentiment polarity.

```
class ReviewData(models.Model):
    user = models.ForeignKey(User, on_delete=models.CASCADE)
    delivery boy = models.ForeignKey(Delivery_Login, on_delete=models.CASCADE, null=True, blank=True)
    title = models.CharField(max_length=100, blank=True)
    review = models.CharField(max_length=500, blank=True)
    image = models.ImageField(upload_to='media', null=True, blank=True)
    sentiment_polarity = models.FloatField(default=0.0)

    def __str__(self):
        return str(self.user)

    def save(self, *args, **kwargs):
        self.sentiment_polarity = self.get_sentiment()
        print('Saving ReviewData:', self)
        super().save(*args, **kwargs)

    def get_sentiment(self):
        blob = TextBlob(self.review)
        sentiment_polarity = blob.sentiment.polarity
        return sentiment_polarity
```

TABLE I. TB_REVIEW

review	image	user_id	delivery_boy_id	sentiment_polarity
good nature		4	manumugesh@gmail.com	0.7
good behavior		4	manumugesh@gmail.com	0.7
good behaviour		2	delnaannaj@gmail.com	0.7
good attitude and so soft.		2	manumugesh@gmail.com	0.3999999999999997
good attitude		2	delnaannaj@gmail.com	0.7
very bad		2	delnaannaj@gmail.com	-0.9099999999999998

VII. RESULT

Graph related to sentiment polarity find from review. It shows sentiment analysis in the range of positive, neutral, negative, highly positive and highly negative respectively of a product.

Using this sentiment analysis I do set to rate each product by taking the polarity of each review.

Using this sentiment analysis I do set to rate each product by taking the polarity of each review.

id	name	product_image	marked_price	selling_price	is_available	cat_id	rating
1	Small Burger	media/top.jpg	125	100	1	1	4.0
2	Crispy Veg Double Patty+ Crispy Veg Double Patty	media/combo.jpg	200	190	1	2	3.0
3	Tikki Twist Burger+ Whooper JR	media/combo2.jpg	210	190	1	2	5.0

And by using the rating of each product I do recommend the most rated product to the user.

Top Rated Products

VIII. CONCLUSION

In this study, we proposed utilizing machine learning to classify reviews. We extracted feedback from clients from the database and evaluated the review data following pre-processing. The processed reviews are classified as positive or negative using Text Blob, a pre-trained model that employs the Nave Bayes algorithm.

In future this model can be became better further by using neural network and deep learning method. It can be used for sentiment analysis of any product which help the customer to recognize the better product by saving time and money.

We may also develop a dynamic web application to categories review data based on ratings and determine consumer satisfaction with the product.

IX. REFERENCES

1. Antony Samuels, John Mcgonical, "Sentiment Analysis on Customer Responses", University of Southern California, Caltech, 5 Jul 2020.
2. Sanjay Dey, Sarhan Wasif, Dhiman Sikder Tonmoy, Subrina Sultana, Jayjeet Sarkar, and Monisha Dey, "A Comparative Study of Support Vector Machine and Naive Bayes Classifier for Sentiment Analysis on Amazon Product Reviews", International Conference on Contemporary Computing and Applications, 217-220, 2020.

3. Lin Zhanga, Kun Huac, Honggang Wangd, Guanqun Qiane, Li Zhang, "Sentiment Analysis on Reviews of Mobile Users", The 11th International Conference on Mobile Systems and Pervasive Computing, 2014.
4. Anant Mahajan, Anshuman Ray, Ashish Verma, Shreya Kohad, Prasheel N Thak are, "Sentiment Analysis using Supervised Machine Learning", International Journal of Advance Research and Innovative Ideas in Education, Vol-6 Issue-6 2020.
5. Kushal Bafna, Durga Toshniwal, "Feature-Based Summarization of Customers' Reviews of Online Products", 17th International Conference in Knowledge Based and Intelligent Information and Engineering Systems, 2013